

Figure 1. LSSDS students attending the introduction course at the AURA Lecture Hall in the AURA campus.
Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Munizaga

The La Serena School for Data Science 2023: 10 Years Training Students and Return to In-Person Format

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There is no question that the new generation of astronomers will do cutting-edge research by taking advantage of the increasingly large datasets that are becoming available. The La Serena School for Data Science (LSSDS) seeks to provide late undergraduate and early graduate students with the tools needed to succeed in this area. Thirty-two students from around the world (United States, China, Senegal, Taiwan, Colombia, Chile, India, México, Ecuador, Brazil) united in La Serena, Chile, for this unforgettable data science experience 7–17 August 2023.

Every year, the LSSDS receives over 200 applications from students of several countries to participate in this intensive school in computational and statistical techniques for data science. The school is offered to undergraduate students in the last years of their programs, and graduate students in the first two years of their programs, in areas such as

Figure 2: LSSDS group photo outside the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/G. Damke

Figure 3: Thirty-two students from around the world attended the LSSDS 2023 on 7–17 August.
Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/M. Paredes

astronomy, physics, biology, medical informatics, computer science, and statistics. The school typically accepts 32–36 applicants comprising ~50 % from US universities, with the remainder coming from Chilean institutions as well as other Latin American countries. Hosted annually at the AURA campus in La Serena, the school has gained popularity since it was launched in 2013. However, the 2020 school was canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the 2021 and 2022 sessions were offered virtually only. The 2023 LSSDS was held in an in-person format.

As in previous years, the 2023 curriculum was crafted by the Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) based partly on the content of the previous — and successful — schools and the feedback from former participants. The School activities were broken down into lectures, hands-on activities, and small group projects. The 2023 School began with an introductory lecture on data science, including data collection. Lecture topics for the first week included introductory statistics, introductory supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods (such as decision trees and

random forests), Bayesian methods, and Gaussian processes. These lectures were complemented by hands-on “laboratories” covering the use of high-performance computing (HPC), databases, time-series analyses, deep learning, and topics related to biology. Most of the curriculum was presented in the form of downloadable Jupyter notebooks, providing the opportunity for students to interactively modify and explore the sample codes and applications discussed during the lectures.

During the second week, the school transitioned into group projects, where students worked together in groups of four to solve a problem using the techniques learned during the first week of school. In total, we conducted eight group projects. An important aspect (incorporated from the online format) was the participation of Teaching/Learning Assistants (TAs). We reached out to our former students from the 2017–2022 schools and invited them to participate as TAs. Funding for their stipends came from a grant we obtained from NSF. The TAs had a crucial role, as they supported the learning of each group during the first week and the development of the group

Figure 4: LSSDS students and faculty tour the Gemini South telescope with Electrical Supervisor Paul Collins.
Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/G. Damke

project. The previous experience of the TAs in the School was crucial because of their familiarity with the curriculum. Additionally, the Local Organizing Committee prepared an “LSSDS welcome package” as a way to generate a *sense of belonging* to the school. The package included items that were useful during the School, a technical book on machine learning to support their learning and serve as a tool for the future, and some souvenir items from the NSF’s NOIRLab telescopes.

During their stay in Chile, the group of students also toured NOIRLab’s telescopes at [Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory](#) and Cerro Pachón, including the [Vera C. Rubin Observatory](#), [SOAR](#), and [Gemini South](#), and ended their day with stargazing led by Guillermo Damke.

The LSSDS offers a unique formative opportunity to introduce highly talented students to data science and big data in a diverse, international, and interdisciplinary environment guided by experts. Since LSSDS began 10 years ago, we have trained more than 230 students in data

science. We are now planning the 2024 session! The school grants full scholarships to cover the roundtrip airfare from the home institutions to La Serena and room and board (except dinners) for the duration of the school. In addition, the school includes a guided visit to the AURA telescopes on Cerro Pachón and Cerro Tololo.

Thanks to our funding from NSF, along with support from other international partners, applications from students in US, Chilean, Ecuadorian (members of CEDIA), and Latin American (members of RedCLARA) institutions are eligible for full scholarships that cover all school expenses. Participants from any data-intensive field are welcome to apply. The announcement of the opening of applications will be made during January through NOIRLab’s social networks and the School website. We look forward to receiving your applications and meeting you in La Serena in August 2024! Please visit the [La Serena School for Data Science: Applied Tools for Data-Driven Sciences](#) website for further information about the School.